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ABSTRACT

A method for creating digital image copyright protection is proposed in this paper. The proposed method in this paper is based on visual cryptography using LPG with PCA. The proposed method is working on selection of random pixels from the original digital image instead of specific selection of pixels. In today's scenario protection of digital data is utmost necessary in every part of life. More robust methods are being developed to protect the proprietary rights of the multimedia. In this paper, an invisible watermarking technique is proposed, to embed multiple binary watermarks into digital medical images based on the concept of Visual Cryptography (VC). The proposed scheme embeds the watermarks without modifying the original host image. Cryptography is nothing but the secret sharing of text. Similarly Visual Cryptography Scheme (VCS) is secret sharing of images. The extension of VCS is Embedded Extended Visual Cryptography. A secret image is divided into shares and stacking of the shares will reveal the secret image. The recovered secret image quality is less in terms of loss of resolution and contrast. In this paper we introduce An Embedded Extended Visual Cryptography Scheme for Color Image using LPG with PCA; this can help to improve the visual quality of the recovered image. Because of local pixel grouping with Principal component Analysis (PCA) because of this we are able to embed and extract multiple secret images with very good quality. This work has been tested and found suitable for its purpose.

KEYWORDS: Embedded Extended Visual Cryptography Scheme (Embedded EVCS), secret sharing, artificial bee colony algorithm.

INTRODUCTION

Technological advancements in both hardware and software are making communication easy and cost effective, which in turn, is producing large volume of digital information being transmitted through the Internet and communication networks. This advancement, in recent years, has created awareness on the risk of piracy and on the importance of protection of content being shared. Several researches have been focused on providing solutions to copyright protection and authentication. These techniques mainly fall into three categories, namely, Steganography, Cryptography and Watermarking. Out of these, watermarking techniques have gained more popularity for proving integrity and authenticity of the owner.

Digital watermarking is defined as an algorithm that can be used to hide secret signal into digital audio, video, image or documents in a manner that does not reduce the overall quality of the original signal. The secret signal, identified as the watermark, can be copyright notices or authentication information or secret text. The original signal is called as „cover signal“ or „host signal“. The process of inserting the secret signal is called embedding and the image after embedding is called „watermarked image“. Extraction or detection is a process that retrieves the stored watermark. Thus the two main components of digital watermarking systems are (i) Embedding and (ii) Extraction. Digital watermark is used in many applications including copyright protection, fingerprinting, copy protection, broadcast monitoring and data authentication. The watermarking techniques are grouped as text-based watermarking, image watermarking, video watermarking, audio watermarking and 3D watermarking. Due to advancement in information and communication technologies, digital media (such as image, video, audio or text) can be easily distributed, duplicated and modified. However, there are some areas where the data cannot be arbitrarily exploited; especially where critical

judgments are made based on the information available in the data. The use of medical images for diagnosis in hospitals is an example of such area. Medical images demand strict security to ensure only the occurrence of legitimate changes. Exchange of medical images between hospitals located in different geographical locations is a common practice now days. But unfortunately, this exchange of medical images through insecure open networks like Internet provides conditions of changes to occur in medical images and consequently creates a threat of undesirable outcome in case, if important information contained in the image is lost or corrupted. Large image databases are to be handled in hospitals need to be protected against malicious attempts. For this purpose, authentication of the medical images can be performed through digital image watermarking.

Digital image watermarking techniques have been developed to protect intellectual property of image in digital form. It is realized by embedding the copyright information, called also "the watermark pattern", into the original image. The watermark pattern in the cover image can be either visible or invisible. However the visible watermarking techniques destroy the image quality and are easily attacked through direct image processing, which increase studies on invisible watermarking. By using the invisible watermarking scheme, the owner can prove his copyrights by extracting the watermark pattern from the watermarked image. There is a lot of medical image watermarking techniques described in the literature, that we can classify in three school thought:

- ROI (Region of Interest) and RONI (Region of Non-Interest) watermarking: in the ROI watermarking techniques, the watermark is embedded in ROI in such away that perceptual quality of image is not compromised. In RONI watermarking techniques, watermark information is embedded in RONI in order to keep the ROI distortion free. This way diagnosis value of medical image is not compromised. In medical images RONI generally contains the black background which encircles the ROI.
- Reversible Watermarking: The second approach corresponds to reversible watermarking. Once the embedded content is read, the watermark can be removed from the image allowing retrieval of the original image.
- Classic watermarking: The third approach consists in using classical watermarking methods while minimizing the distortion. In that case, the watermark replaces some image details such as the least significant bit of the image or details lost after lossy image compression. Medical image watermarking techniques can also be grouped into two main categories. In the first one, the watermark is embedded in the spatial domain by directly modifying the pixel intensity of the original image, and in the second one, the watermark is embedded in the transform domain, such as Complex Cosine Transform (DCT), Complex Fourier Transform (DFT) and Complex Wavelet Transform (DWT) etc. In general, the DWT produces watermark images with the best visual quality due to the absence of blocking artifacts. However, it has two drawbacks:
 - Lack of shift invariance, which means that small shifts in the input signal can cause major variations in the distribution of energy between DWT coefficients at different scales.
 - Poor directional selectivity for diagonal features, because the wavelet filters are separable and real. To overcome these problems, Kingsbury introduced the design and implementation of 2-D multi-scale transform, called Complex Dual Tree Wavelet Transform (DT-CWT), that represent edges more efficiently than does the DWT.

In the few last years, we find out the apparition of a new range of watermarking techniques using the concept of Visual Cryptography (VC). The act of decryption is to simply stack shares and view the secret image that appears on the stacked shares. The decoding of the secret image by the Human Visual System (HVS) is the interesting feature that has attracted the researchers in adapting this concept for several applications including watermarking. In accordance with cryptography, the security of a crypto-system does not reside in the algorithm, but resides in the secret key; that is, the security will maintain well even if the algorithm has been published. In the watermarking schemes using VC, the watermark pattern can be either physically embedded into the cover image or not. The first category schemes which are similar to traditional methods are called watermark embedding schemes. The second category are called watermark concealing schemes, they are particularly useful in protecting highly sensitive images, since the original image is not altered. This last feature has attracted us to use this concept for medical images watermarking, due to the high sensitivity of medical image. In this way our medical images may remain intact and protected from illegitimate changes in the same time.

In this paper, we have prearranged for a brief overview about the proposed hybrid model optimization in which the embedding and extracting algorithms of watermarking in Complex wavelet transform are combined with GA based

optimization techniques for watermarking. The key parameters to be concentrated for this proposed model are orthogonality, symmetry and compact support which will enable the model to achieve a better watermarked media and robustness in watermarking. The watermarking technique proposed in this work may be very effective against different low-frequency an attack that demolishes the low frequency component of the image.

Embedding Process

In Embedding process, we have the inputs: original image and one watermark image, and output is watermarked image. By using Haar wavelet transform, the original image is decomposed into four sub-bands like HH, LL, HL and LH for embedding watermark image. Choose the HL and LH sub-bands for embedding the watermark image from the four sub-bands. Most techniques are utilizing these aforementioned two parts only for this purpose. So, here also we are using these parts because producing high PSNR and robustness for hiding information in different media and approximation coefficients are thought to be reasonably firm and less sensitive to slight changes of the image pixel, they are the perfect embedding area. Based on artificial intelligent method, the coefficients at widespread sub-bands HL and LH are chosen for watermark embedding, in order to attain a balance between robustness and fidelity. The watermarking pixels are, at the same time, embedded into the HL and LH sub-band based on the some steps. In the embedding process we used the GA and BFO for the checking of the fitness of the stego message. A genetic algorithm (GA) is a method for solving both constrained and unconstrained optimization problems based on a natural selection process that mimics biological evolution. The algorithm repeatedly modifies a population of individual solutions. At each step, the genetic algorithm randomly selects individuals from the current population and uses them as parents to produce the children for the next generation. Over successive generations, the population "evolves" toward an optimal solution. You can apply the genetic algorithm to solve problems that are not well suited for standard optimization algorithms, including problems in which the objective function is discontinuous, non differentiable, stochastic, or highly nonlinear. When we use GA in the purposed work then we got the more accuracy than other techniques.

Extraction Process

Here the inputs are watermarked image I , size of the watermarking image I_s , and an output is extracted watermarking image I_o . Due to wavelet transform the obtained watermarked image is decomposed into different sub bands such as HH, HL, LH and LL for extracting the watermark image. In order to achieve both quality of watermarked media and robustness of the watermarked media, we use the Genetic algorithm (GA) and BFO algorithm. In this work GA for generating the chromosomes .GA optimization techniques are applied in embedding and extraction process. So we can take the watermarked media parameters like intensity, etc., for computing PSNR and BER of the watermarked media. These values are based on the original media size and intensity. The optimization process of GA is described as follows.

Genetic Algorithm

Genetic Algorithm (GA) An evolutionary algorithm which generates each individual from some encoded form known as a "chromosome" or "genome". Chromosomes are combined or mutated to breed new individuals. "Crossover", the kind of recombination of chromosomes found in sexual reproduction in nature, is often also used in GAs. Here, an offspring's chromosome is created by joining segments chosen alternately from each of two parent's chromosomes which are of fixed length. GA is useful for multidimensional optimization problems in which the chromosome can encode the values for the different variables being optimized.

Generation of Chromosome

The function of the randomly generated set of chromosomes (set of genes) is the generation of chromosomes. Presently, population size plays an important role in presenting the solution to the problem at hand. The beginning population set up is done by producing a population set P that comprises of set of chromosome vectors having half size of the HL or LH sub-band. Subsequently, we have placed the one's value with the size of the watermarked (hiding) media in that vector in a random manner. And, the remaining cases are filled down by zero value. Then, the beginning set of chromosomes is brought forth at random with minimum number.

Fitness Computation

Finding the optimized solution to the chromosomes is the better way. Till finding the locations defined in the chromosomes for each chromosome in the population set, the watermarking embedding process is iterated. Here

embedding and extraction process is carried out using these procedures which were. Then the fitness of GA is calculated by us, which is utilized for calculating PSNR along with the measure of BER value. Below cited the formula is for discovering the fitness value of PSO. Fitness computation formula is depicted below,

$$\text{Fitness} = \text{PSNR} + \text{BER}$$

There are some parameters are give which used in this papers.

A. MSE:

Mean Squared Error is essentially a signal fidelity measure. The goal of a signal fidelity measure is to compare two signals by providing a quantitative score that describes the degree of similarity/fidelity or, conversely, the level of error/distortion between them. Usually, it is assumed that one of the signals is a pristine original, while the other is distorted or contaminated by errors. The MSE between the signals is given by the following formula:

$$\text{MSE} = (1/N) \sum_i |x(i) - e(i)|^2$$

Here x and e are the encrypted watermarked audio signals respectively and N is the number of samples in the audio signal.

B. BER:

Bit error rate refers to the amount of watermark data that may be reliably embedded within a host signal per unit of time or space, such as bits per second or bits per pixel. A higher bit rate may be desirable in some applications in order to embed more copyright information. In this study, reliability was measured as the bit error rate (BER) of extracted watermark data. The BER (in percent) is given by the expression:

$$Q(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_x^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{u^2}{2}\right) du$$

Where x is a function of the block size.

C. PERCEPTUAL QUALITY:

Perceptual quality refers to the imperceptibility of embedded watermark data within the host signal. In most applications, it is important that the watermark is undetectable to a listener or viewer. This ensures that the quality of the host signal is not perceptibly distorted, and does not indicate the presence or location of a watermark. In this study, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the watermarked signal versus the host signal was used as a quality measure:

$$\text{SNR} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left\{ \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x^2(n)}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} [\tilde{x}(n) - x(n)]^2} \right\}$$

D. PSNR

Embedding this extra data must not degrade human perception about the object. Namely, the watermark should be “invisible” in a watermarked image or “inaudible” in watermarked digital music. Evaluation of imperceptibility is usually based on an objective measure of quality, called peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR), or a subjective test with specified procedures. The PSNR values can be obtained using following formula-

$$\text{PSNR} = 20 \log_{10} (\text{PIXEL_VALUE} / \sqrt{\text{MSE}})$$

These all given parameters are important factor in watermarking techniques.

E. Local Pixel Grouping (LPG)-PCA

In this paper we present LPG-PCA technique for noise removal in an image. PCA is a de-correlation technique in statistical signal processing used pervasively in pattern recognition. By transforming the image data set into PCA domain and preserving only the desired components the noise and other trivial information can be removed considerably. In the proposed LPG-PCA algorithm the input dataset to PCA is obtained using the block match LPG technique. Here the pixels and its neighbors are modeled as vectors and the training samples are determined by selecting the pixels with similar properties within the local window. This algorithm ensures effective noise removal

and edge preservation. The algorithm is computed in two stages for effectiveness. Here we assume that the noise (u) in the image is additive, with zero mean and standard deviation σ . Let this noise be added to the original image say F . Therefore the new image value is determined as $F_u = F + u$. The goal of our project is to find an image F_1 which is approximately equal to the original image F . Pixels are identified based on the spatial coordinates and their grey scale value (intensity value) whereas of different intensity values. Here we assume the pixels in local structure as vectors and improve the edge preservation process. The image F and noise u are uncorrelated. For removing noise from an underlying pixel, according to the fig, a $K \times K$ matrix centered on the pixel and denote by $X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m]^T$ with total no of elements $m = k^2$. The window is centered on the image X . Since the image is prone to noise u we represent the new image vector as $X_u = X + u$. The noisy image where $U = [u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m]^T$. The statistical PCA is used on these vectors. To remove the noise from an image the covariance matrix X_u and PCA transformation matrix are to be calculated. Therefore, we use a LL training block centered on X_u , such that $L \times L$ is greater than $K \times K$. From the training block we need to estimate the required pixels for the PCA. This selection of different pixels from training blocks is a complex process and may sometimes leads to inaccurate results.

EVALUATION AND RESULTS

To verify the effectiveness (qualities and robustness) of the proposed Medical Image Watermarking we conduct several experiments with this procedure on several images. The methodology of our proposed work is given below:

Phase1: Firstly we develop a particular GUI for this implementation. After that we develop a code for the loading the original image and message image or message in the Matlab database.

Phase2: Develop a code for the Complex Wavelet Transform and Inverse Complex Wavelet Transform with partitioning technique. After that we apply CWT on the selected image and develop code for Visual Cryptography with LPG. When we apply the GA on the image then we got more accuracy than another technique.

Phase3: Develop a code for the finding the watermarked data. Then we got the image with message data this is called Embedding technique. For the embedding process we apply the key for the security purpose.

Phase4: After that we develop code for the extraction process using PCA. Within the extraction process we develop code for the message extraction from the watermarked file using ICWT. After the extraction process we got the original image and message data by using the key.

CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this paper we propose "An Embedded Extended Visual Cryptography Scheme for Color Image using LPG with PCA". It includes the Embedded Extended Visual Cryptography Scheme for Color Images using Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) Algorithm. Here the implementations are done with the pixel expansion of four. That means the pixel is divided into four sub pixels. but, in our propose work "An Embedded Extended Visual Cryptography Scheme for Color Image using LPG with PCA" For each processed patch and pixel, similar patches are searched with pixel in spatial domain and throughout all coil elements, and arranged in appropriate matrix forms. Then, noise and aliasing artifacts are removed from the structured matrix by applying Local Pixel Grouping using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). In this paper, we use local pixel groping with Principal component Analysis (PCA) because of this we able to embed and extract multiple secret image with very good quality. The main objectives of propose works are Embed two secret images in one cover image. Better visual quality for the decrypted image. High PSNR value. Calculate structural similarity index matrix (SSIM).

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